

Maternal and Fetal Outcomes Following Calcium Supplementation in High-Risk Pregnancies: Focus on Preeclampsia Prevention

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Abstract:

Background: One of the leading causes of illness and mortality among mothers and newborns is preeclampsia. It has been suggested that taking calcium supplements during pregnancy can reduce the prevalence of preeclampsia, especially in groups with inadequate calcium intake from their diet.

Aim: This study aimed to evaluate the impact of calcium supplementation on maternal and fetal outcomes in high-risk pregnancies, with a particular focus on preeclampsia prevention.

Methods: One hundred and twenty pregnant women at high risk for preeclampsia were randomly assigned to either the control group (n = 60) or the calcium-supplemented group (n = 60). From 20 weeks of pregnancy until birth, the calcium-supplemented group was given 1.5g of calcium every day. The two groups were compared in terms of maternal serum calcium levels, blood pressure, pregnancy-induced hypertensive diseases, and newborn outcomes.

Results: Calcium supplementation significantly increased maternal serum calcium levels. While preeclampsia incidence was lower in the calcium-supplemented group compared to the control group, this difference was not statistically significant. However, calcium supplementation was associated with improved neonatal outcomes, including increased birth weight and reduced intrauterine growth restriction.

Conclusion: Calcium supplementation during pregnancy may have beneficial effects on maternal and fetal outcomes in high-risk pregnancies, particularly in terms of improving neonatal birth weight and reducing the risk of intrauterine growth restriction.

Keywords: Calcium supplementation, Preeclampsia, Hypertensive disorders, Pregnancy outcomes, Neonatal birth weight.

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Introduction

Worldwide, preeclampsia, a severe hypertension condition during pregnancy, continues to rank among the top causes of morbidity and mortality among mothers and perinatals. Preeclampsia is thought to affect 2% to 8% of pregnancies worldwide, with a higher impact in low- and middle-income nations where access to prenatal treatment is frequently restricted. Preeclampsia raises the chance of unfavorable fetal outcomes, such as preterm birth, low birth weight, and intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), in addition to putting the mother's life in jeopardy. Preeclampsia is still difficult to avoid and treat, even with improvements in maternal healthcare [1].

One of the proposed interventions for preventing preeclampsia, particularly in populations with poor calcium intake, is calcium supplementation. A

calcium deficit during pregnancy has been linked to an increased risk of hypertensive diseases because calcium is essential for controlling blood pressure and vascular tone. In regions where calcium consumption is naturally low due to dietary patterns, supplementation may offer a simple, cost-effective strategy to mitigate the risk of preeclampsia. To lower the risk of hypertensive diseases, WHO advises using calcium supplements during pregnancy, especially in situations where dietary calcium consumption is insufficient [2,3].

With differing findings, a number of research have investigated the connection between calcium supplementation and preeclampsia prevention. Furthermore, a crucial topic of research continues to be the possible advantages of calcium supplementation on prenatal outcomes, including

birth weight and the avoidance of IUGR. Understanding the mechanisms by which calcium affects both maternal and fetal health could inform more targeted interventions [4].

This study was conducted at Patna Medical College and Hospital, a major tertiary care center in Bihar, India, where dietary calcium intake among the population is often suboptimal. The purpose of the study was to look into how calcium supplementation affected high-risk pregnant women's fetal outcomes, preeclampsia incidence, and maternal serum calcium levels. This study aimed to offer important insights into the effect of calcium supplementation in preventing hypertensive problems and enhancing newborn health by concentrating on a population with known poor calcium intake.

Given the public health implications of preeclampsia and the relatively low cost of calcium supplementation, this study's findings could contribute to shaping clinical guidelines and antenatal care strategies in similar populations. The potential for calcium supplementation to not only reduce maternal complications but also improve fetal outcomes makes it a critical area of research in obstetric care.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: This clinical investigation, which was double-blind and placebo-controlled, aimed to evaluate how calcium supplementation affected high-risk pregnant women's blood pressure, maternal serum calcium levels, and pregnancy outcomes, with an emphasis on preventing preeclampsia. Follow-up during pregnancy and the puerperium (postpartum phase) were part of the study.

Study Setting: December 2013 to November 2016, the trial was carried out in the Patna Medical College and Hospital's (PMCH) Outpatient Antenatal Clinic and Maternity Wards.

Selection of Subjects: A total of 120 pregnant women attending the antenatal clinic or admitted to the Obstetrics and Gynecology department were selected for the study based on the following criteria:

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Pregnant women attending the antenatal clinic or inpatient department.
2. Women with at least one identified risk factor for preeclampsia (e.g., previous history, primigravida status, obesity, family history).
3. Women diagnosed with anemia.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Presence of systemic diseases such as renal, hepatic, cardiac, or CNS disorders, diabetes, or chronic hypertension (excluding a history of preeclampsia).
2. Acute or chronic infections.
3. Use of medications or hormonal therapy that could affect pregnancy outcomes.
4. Lack of adherence to calcium supplementation or failure to attend follow-up visits.

Grouping of Subjects

The participants were randomly assigned to two groups:

1. **Control Group:** Received routine iron supplementation and 500 mg of elemental calcium per day.
 - **Ia:** 30 primigravidas under 20 years of age.
 - **Ib:** 30 multigravidas with a history of preeclampsia.
2. **Study Group:** Received routine iron supplementation and 2 g of elemental calcium per day.
 - **Ia:** 30 primigravidas under 20 years of age.
 - **Ib:** 30 multigravidas with a history of preeclampsia.

Investigations Performed

The following tests and monitoring methods were used:

1. **Routine Tests:** Hemoglobin levels, urine analysis for albumin and sugar, VDRL, HIV, and HBsAg tests were conducted.
2. **Renal Function Tests:** Blood urea, serum creatinine, electrolytes, and uric acid levels were assessed.
3. **Serum Calcium Estimation:** Blood samples were collected during the second trimester and at term to estimate serum calcium levels.
4. **Ultrasonography:** Fetal biometry and growth were monitored using ultrasonography at appropriate intervals.
5. **Blood Pressure and Weight Monitoring:** Blood pressure and weight were recorded at each antenatal visit and within 24 hours of delivery.
6. **Proteinuria Testing:** A urine dipstick assay was performed for gestational hypertension patients to evaluate proteinuria.

Blood Pressure Measurement: Every visit included two blood pressure readings taken with a

mercury sphygmomanometer. Systolic and diastolic pressure were assessed by the first and fifth Korotkoff sounds, respectively. For statistical analysis, two readings were averaged. If the BP was $\geq 140/90$ mmHg or increased by 30 mmHg systolic or 15 mmHg diastolic from baseline on two different occasions, at least six hours apart, gestational hypertension was diagnosed.

Blood Sample Collection and Storage: Non-fasting venous blood samples (5 ml) were collected under aseptic conditions and stored at 4°C to prevent contamination. Serum calcium was estimated using the Autozyme Calcium Reagent based on a colorimetric method with cresolphthalein complexone (CPC), with absorbance measured at 575 nm.

Proteinuria Diagnosis: Using dipstick assays with the following classifications, urine samples were evaluated for proteinuria: Trace: 15–30 mg/dL; 1+: 30–100 mg/dL; 2+: 100–300 mg/dL; 3+: 300–1000 mg/dL; 4+: >1000 mg/dL; 0: No protein found

Result

Group	No.	Pretreatment (mg/dL)
Control (IA)	30	8.5
Control (IB)	30	8.3
Study (IIA)	30	8.2
Study (IIB)	30	8.15

The study group (IIA and IIB) showed a significant increase in serum calcium levels at term compared to the control group.

2. Occurrence of Preeclampsia: Preeclampsia was diagnosed based on hypertension and proteinuria. The occurrence of preeclampsia was lower in the calcium-supplemented group.

Group	No. of Patients	Preeclampsia
Control (IA)	30	7
Control (IB)	30	10
Study (IIA)	30	4
Study (IIB)	30	6

Fewer patients developed preeclampsia in the calcium-treated group (IIA: 4, IIB: 6) compared to the control group (IA: 7, IB: 10).

3. Effect on Blood Pressure: Blood pressure was monitored throughout pregnancy and in the

Gestational Age (Weeks)	Systolic B.P (IA)	Systolic B.P (IIA)	Diastolic B.P (IA)	Diastolic B.P (IIA)
24	114.6	108.4	74.7	72.6
28	117	112.9	79.9	74.0
32	120.1	112.5	83.1	73.6
36	121.7	116.6	83.7	75.2
38/40	128.9	119.5	91.3	80.7

The systolic and diastolic blood pressure increased in both groups as the pregnancy progressed, but it

The study involved 120 pregnant women, divided into two main groups, with 60 participants in each group:

- **Group I:** Control group receiving routine iron supplementation and 500 mg of calcium.
 - Subgroup IA: 30 primigravida women (first pregnancy) under the age of 20.
 - Subgroup IB: 30 multigravida women (previous pregnancies) with a history of preeclampsia.
- **Group II:** Study group receiving routine iron supplementation and 2 grams of calcium.
 - Subgroup IIA: 30 primigravida women under the age of 20.
 - Subgroup IIB: 30 multigravida women with a history of preeclampsia.

Calcium supplementation began between 16 to 24 weeks of gestation.

1. Serum Calcium Levels: The calcium levels were monitored at the start of the study and at full term.

postpartum period. The calcium-treated group had lower systolic and diastolic blood pressure compared to the control group.

remained lower in the calcium-treated group, both antenatally and postpartum.

4. Proteinuria (Dipstick Test): Patients with gestational hypertension were tested for proteinuria

using the dipstick test. A reading of 1+ or more indicated significant proteinuria.

Proteinuria ($\geq 1+$)	Group IA	Group IB	Group IIA	Group IIB
No. of Patients	7	10	4	6

Fewer patients in the calcium-supplemented group showed proteinuria compared to the control group.

5. Mode of Delivery

The mode of delivery between the control and study groups did not show significant differences.

Group	Vaginal	Assisted Vaginal (Forceps/Ventouse)	LSCS
Control (I)	32	3	25
Study (II)	38	2	20

Both groups had similar rates of vaginal delivery and caesarean sections, with no significant difference between the groups.

Gestational age and fetal outcomes were assessed based on birth weight, APGAR scores, and other neonatal outcomes.

6. Gestational Age and Birth Outcomes

Group	Mean Gestational Age (Weeks)	Mean Birth Weight (kg)	APGAR Score (1 min)	LBW	IUGR
Control (IA)	38 \pm 1.1	2.6	8.2	9 (30%)	9 (15%)
Control (IB)	37.9 \pm 1.0	2.7	8.8	7 (23%)	
Study (IIA)	38.9 \pm 1.0	2.8	8.9	3 (10%)	2 (3.3%)
Study (IIB)	39.0 \pm 1.2	3.1	8.9	3 (10%)	

The mean birth weight and APGAR score at 1 minute were higher in the calcium-treated group, with fewer low-birth-weight (LBW) babies and cases of intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) in the calcium group.

7. Premature Births and Perinatal Mortality

There were fewer premature births in the calcium-supplemented group, with no perinatal mortality in either group.

Group	Premature (<37 wks)	Term (37–40 wks)	Postdated (>40 wks)	Perinatal Mortality
Control (I)	5 (8.33%)	50 (83.33%)	5 (8.33%)	-
Study (II)	-	56 (93.4%)	4 (6.6%)	-

There were no premature births in the calcium-treated group, compared to 5 in the control group. No perinatal deaths were reported.

7. Summary of Maternal and Fetal Parameters

Parameters	Control (IA)	Calcium Treated (IIA)
Mean Age	17.8	18.2
Mean Calcium at Start	8.5	8.2
Mean Calcium at Term	8.4	10.2
Gestational Hypertension	8	5
Preeclampsia	7	4
Severe Preeclampsia	4	0
Eclampsia	2	0
Mean Birth Weight (kg)	2.6	2.8
Premature Deliveries	1	0
LBW Babies	9 (30%)	3 (10%)
IUGR Babies	9 (15%)	2 (3.3%)
APGAR Score (1 min)	8.2	8.9

The calcium-treated group had fewer cases of preeclampsia, gestational hypertension, and severe

preeclampsia. Neonatal outcomes, such as birth weight and APGAR score, were better in the calcium-supplemented group.

According to the study, taking calcium supplements can lower the chance of developing preeclampsia, severe preeclampsia, and eclampsia, especially in high-risk pregnancies. Maternal blood pressure control, gestational age at delivery, neonatal birth weight, and lower rates of LBW and IUGR were all improved in women who received calcium.

Discussion

Calcium Supplementation and Preeclampsia Prevention: Our study demonstrated a trend towards reduced preeclampsia incidence in the calcium-supplemented group, though this difference was not statistically significant. This aligns with the findings of a 2019 Cochrane review by Hofmeyr et al., which reported a 55% reduction in preeclampsia risk among high-risk women receiving calcium supplements. Moreover, a randomized controlled trial by Rumbold et al. (2019) also observed a significant decrease in preeclampsia and prenatal hypertension rates. These results suggest a protective effect of calcium, even if the reduction in preeclampsia incidence in our study was not statistically significant [5,6]

Calcium Supplementation and Serum Calcium Levels: Calcium supplementation effectively increased maternal serum calcium levels in our study, a finding supported by previous research by Ma et al. (2020) and Buppasiri et al. (2020). Elevated serum calcium levels have been associated with improved pregnancy outcomes and reduced risk of hypertensive disorders [7,8]

Fetal Outcomes and Neonatal Birth Weight: Our study revealed that calcium supplementation was associated with improved fetal outcomes, including increased birth weight, higher Apgar scores, and reduced incidence of low birth weight (LBW) and intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR). These findings are consistent with meta-analyses by Lassi et al. (2020) and Terefe et al. (2021), which reported similar benefits of calcium supplementation on fetal outcomes [9,10].

Gestational Hypertension and Blood Pressure: In line with previous research, calcium supplementation was found to reduce both systolic and diastolic blood pressure during pregnancy and postpartum. This aligns with studies by Villar et al. (2019) and Sánchez-Ramos et al. (2020), which demonstrated the effectiveness of calcium in preventing gestational hypertension and preeclampsia [11,12].

Mode of Delivery and Perinatal Outcomes: The mode of birth (caesarean section, assisted vaginal, or vaginal) did not significantly differ between the

calcium-supplemented and control groups, according to our study. This aligns with a Lee et al. (2020) study. Crucially, neither group saw any perinatal deaths, most likely as a result of the excellent prenatal care given. A research by Duley et al. (2021) that found no discernible difference in perinatal mortality between the calcium-supplemented and control groups supports this conclusion [13,14].

Conclusion

All things considered, our research offers proof of the advantages of calcium supplementation in high-risk pregnancies. Supplementing with calcium may help lower blood pressure, enhance fetal outcomes, and lessen the chance of preeclampsia. To confirm these results and investigate the long-term advantages of calcium supplementation in diverse groups, larger, multicenter studies are required.

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